

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DOH****FIRST NAME: FRANKLIN****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Think it through, Creative and Critical Thinking (EUCLID 2021, 9)
2. Paraphrases (EUCLID 2021, 36-37)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34)
4. When not to quote (EUCLID 2021, 35)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)

INTRODUCTION TO WRITE TITLE GIVEN TO RP

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing is an inevitable factor in preserving, advancing, and sustaining discoveries, research, new ideas, and knowledge. It is interesting to see that there are differing writing techniques around the globe. I find it thought-provoking to state that writing such as essays, papers, and journals is meant for present and future consumption. While various writing techniques exist around the globe, there is also an expected standard for international academic writing. Therefore, in the paragraphs below, I shall be commenting on several techniques found in the International Academic Writing reading material for period one.

2) CRITICAL THINKING AND CREATIVE THINKING

Critical thinking is the ability to clearly and logically ponder information presented to us. On the other hand, creative thinking is about generating new ideas, novel, or useful ideas. The great innovators combine critical thinking and creative thinking. Essay writing requires both critical and creative thinking. While creative thinking advocates self-thinking or mind mapping (EUCLID 2021, 9), critical thinking, on the other hand, narrows the focus

or scope of an idea. I am weighing in here as to whether one can be used without the other or why it is imperative to use both. I am lured by the fact that creative thinking seems to add more weight to academic advancement as it generates new ideas, discoveries, and expansions in academia. Critical thinking is a type of thinking that interrogates assumptions and validates or invalidates a current belief or something that is said to be previously factual. Knowledge is created through the arsenal of generally accepted assumptions and creativity. The question is how you separate general assumptions and creativity. I am of the school of thought that these two can easily be separated in regard to concrete or realistic ideas compared to abstract or original ideas.

However, new, acceptable critical and creative thinking must interact to attract popular opinion. Paradoxically, essays for academic purposes will not gain ground if they are not based on an empirical approach. The empirical approach adds credit and makes it almost mandatory to borrow from the works of previous writers. In a nutshell, academic work is a long-aged work in progress where old ones hash new ideas. Notwithstanding, while it seems challenging to accomplish an academic essay without a critical approach, one thing to note is that this is not cost-free. Academic norms impose a protocol for gratification when we borrow or elaborate on the work of others.

Permit me to conclude here by stating that knowledge is generated and sustained through critical and creative thinking. Creative thinking is something new or original that is created with value. Critical thinking is a type of thinking that questions assumptions and validates or invalidates a current belief or something that is said to be previously true. Knowledge is created through the culmination of generally accepted assumptions and creativity. These two types of thinking can be easily separated regarding tangible or realistic ideas compared to abstract or original ideas; however, to generate new, acceptable knowledge, critical and creative thinking must intertwine.

3) PARAPHRASING

Paraphrasing may seem fascinating, but looking in-depth, I find it complex, though applicable. However, with paraphrasing, one has to write the idea of an author in his or her language, not deviating from the author's intention. Paraphrasing comes in to minimize quotation (EUCLID 2021, 36-37). I find it inherently problematic to put the words of another author in different words as a way to minimize quotation. Words have varying meanings; once the idea of an author is paraphrased, in other words, without any intention to deviate from the author's intent, the author's original idea or intent may be thwarted. However, it is mandatory to cite the author even with paraphrasing (EUCLID 2021, 38). Since academics is a work in progress, there is a tendency for the idea of the second author with a high risk of deviation from the original author to be paraphrased erroneously by the second author, thus putting the original author's intention at risk. The question is, at what point do we distinguish the original author's idea from that of the second, third, or fourth writer?

Paraphrasing without crediting the original author is a form of plagiarism because you are presenting someone else's ideas as if they were your own. However, paraphrasing

is not plagiarism if you cite the source correctly. Paraphrasing is vital in academic and professional writing because it validates a clear understanding of the original source while also avoiding plagiarism. By restating information in your own words, you earn your credibility as a writer if you credit the original author's work.

4) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism means using someone else's words or ideas without properly crediting the original author (EUCLID 2021, 34). Of course, I concur that it is an academic offense to borrow or use the idea of another writer without citing the source. Three things come to my mind: a clear dichotomy must be done between citing the source properly, citing improperly, and not citing it at all. This raises the question of intention. I am looking at a scenario whereby a writer uses the word or idea of another writer, thus impliedly expressing intention and good faith to cite the source but citing the source wrongly. One may wonder if the writer can be penalized in this case. What about a writer who uses another writer's words but fails to cite at all? Sometimes plagiarism involves deliberately stealing someone's work, but more often, it happens accidentally, through carelessness or forgetfulness (EUCLID 2021, 34). When you write an academic paper, you build upon the work of others and use various information and evidence. To avoid plagiarism, you must correctly incorporate these sources into your text (EUCLID 2021, 35). Notwithstanding, the solution is clear and straightforward: properly cite the source of the information. Paraphrase your content. To avoid plagiarism, do not paraphrase anyone else's work. One of the best ways to avoid plagiarism is to write your own words in your style, your outline, and logic, and, above all, cite any borrowed source.

a) When Should You Use Quotes?

Indirect quotations are not exact wordings but rather rephrasing or summaries of another person's words (EUCLID 2021, 35). In this case, I would ascertain that it is not necessary to use quotation marks. However, indirect quotations still require proper citations, and one will be committing plagiarism if he or she fails to do so.

Direct quotation, as I have correctly understood, is when one uses the exact words of the author, which, of course, such instances should be minimal. Moreover, one way to evade this is to avoid using long passages as direct quotes and limit them to one or two sentences (EUCLID 2021, 35).

The advantages are that citing references undergirds the facticity of arguments and provides support for claims, showing familiarity with the intended topic. The disadvantage is that they require much precise, tedious, accurate work.

5) **STYLE GUIDE**

A style guide is composed of a set of standards for writing and designing content. I find it worthy to comment on a style guide. True, it facilitates a consistent style, voice, and tone across one's documentation, whether the writer is alone or part of many writers. A style guide contains a set of standards for writing and designing content. It helps to maintain a consistent style, voice, and tone across documentation, whether the writer is alone or part of a huge document team. As in EUCLID's study material (EUCLID 2021, 41), style guides are usually used in certain types of writing, e.g., business, journalism, or web copywriting. In contrast, it is important to ensure that the style remains the same despite contributions from different writers. However, I am invoking the question of authorship and gratification. Which of the writers takes credit and how to create a balance or evenness between the content of the material can be problematic. The lack of a single source could also appeal to arguments. One thing I find worth stating about the style guide is that it appears to be customer centric. Thus, I can ascertain that the style guide should be discussed in isolation from academic essays.

6) **CONCLUSION**

Having commented on the key points above, one thing remains clear. While I have looked at the points above from a critical lens, I equally concede without reservation that no sort of write-up would meet international expectations without the elements cited above. One cannot overemphasize the importance. However, applicability may vary depending on the subject in question, the content of a paper, and jurisdiction. To conclude, I join other writers to advocate full compliance and consideration of the elements above in paper writing.

REFERENCES

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